

H2020 - Research and Innovation Action

APPLICATE

Advanced Prediction in Polar regions and beyond: Modelling, observing system design and Linkages associated with a Changing Arctic climaTE

Grant Agreement No: 727862

Deliverable 8.8

First report on the content and extent of joint activities with collaborators in USA and Canada

Submission of Deliverable

Work Package	WP8 Clustering		
Deliverable No	8.8		
Deliverable title	First report on the content and extent of joint activities with collaborators in USA and Canada		
Version	1		
Status	Final		
Dissemination level	PU - Public		
Lead Beneficiary	1 - AWI		
Contributors	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 – AWI	<input type="checkbox"/> 2 – BSC	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 3 - ECMWF
	<input type="checkbox"/> 4 – UiB	<input type="checkbox"/> 5 – UNI Research	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 6 – MET Norway
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 7 – Met Office	<input type="checkbox"/> 8 – UCL	<input type="checkbox"/> 9 - UREAD
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 10 – SU	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 11 – CNRS-GAME	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 12 - CERFACS
	<input type="checkbox"/> 13 – AP	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 14 – UiT	<input type="checkbox"/> 15 - IORAS
	<input type="checkbox"/> 16 - MGO		
Due Date	30 April 2018		
Delivery Date	30 April 2018		

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research & Innovation programme under grant agreement No. 727862.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

There are a number of collaborations between APPLICATE partners and groups in the USA and Canada. Effective clustering for these activities happens both in terms of science coordination as well as at scientific levels. As part of WP8 on Clustering scientific collaborations that are directly or indirectly related to the project activities have been tracked. This document contains a non-exhaustive list of activities as reported by APPLICATE partners on their current and most significant engagements with collaborators from North America.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background and motivation

Advancing polar predictive capacity in the Arctic and understanding the impact of Arctic climate change on the weather and climate in midlatitudes has attracted considerable attention in recent years. It is not surprising, thus, that there are numerous projects both in Europe and North America tackling these issues. The advantage is that there is now the critical mass needed to make much needed progress. However, in order to avoid unnecessary duplication and exploit synergies, effective clustering is needed. The clustering concept employed in the APPLICATE project for activities with partners in Europe and North America is outlined in the Clustering Plan (i.e., Milestone MS18).

There are a number of collaborations between APPLICATE partners and groups in the USA and Canada that are related to key activities of the APPLICATE project. Effective clustering for these activities happens at both coordination and scientific levels. As part of WP8 on Clustering scientific collaborations that are directly or indirectly related to the project activities have been tracked. This document contains a non-exhaustive list of activities as reported by APPLICATE partners on their current and most significant engagements with collaborators in North America.

2. REPORT ON JOINT ACTIVITIES WITH USA AND CANADA

2.1. Main partners

APPLICATE contributes to implementing the Transatlantic Ocean Research Alliance¹ through strong collaboration with coordinating bodies and numerous individual collaborators from the US and Canada. Some partners are listed in Table 1 along with the main contact points.

Table 1: List of major partners in USA and Canada for which clustering activities are carried out (in alphabetic order).

Partner	Points of contact
Canada	
Environment and Climate Change Canada (ECCC)	Barbara Casati Bertrand Denis Stephane Laroche Pierre Pellerin Gilbert Brunet Bill Marryfield
University of Toronto	Paul Kushner
United States	

¹ <http://ec.europa.eu/research/iscp/index.cfm?pg=transatlantic-alliance>

McGill University	Bruno Tremblay
National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR)	Julio Bacmeister Gokhan Danabasoglu Andrew Gettelman Cecile Hannay Marika Holland
National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA)	Mitch Bushuk Taneil Uttal Michael Winton
Sea Ice Prediction Network (SIPN)	Cecilia Bitz Edward Blanchard- Wrigglesworth
University of California Irvine	Yannick Peings
US CLIVAR Working Group on Arctic-Midlatitude Linkages	Judah Cohen Xiangdong Zhang

High-level coordination between the different activities is ensured by effective communication between the coordination offices of the various projects, participation/representation in each other's annual meetings, and organisation of joint events at international conferences. Scientific coordination is carried out by several individuals in the APPLICATE team.

2.2. Activities involving APPLICATE team members

APPLICATE is making a substantial contribution to the Year of Polar Prediction (YOPP)— As one of the deliverables of the Arctic Science Ministerial². For example, Arctic Climate Across Scales (ACAS) is a YOPP-endorsed project funded by the Knut and Alice Wallenberg foundation that is closely connected to APPLICATE, with one key target being the development of observation capabilities in the Arctic by deploying instruments on the Swedish icebreaker Oden. During the Swedish "Arctic Ocean 2018" (AO2018) field experiment during July and August 2018, ACAS makes its first deployment with a suite of different instruments, including 6-hourly radiosoundings. The soundings are performed in collaboration with ECCC, who supply the radiosondes for this campaign. These soundings form the backbone for all the atmospheric observations and are necessary for carrying out cutting-edge research. Additionally, the 6-hourly soundings will be transmitted in near-real time to the GTS so that they can be used by operational prediction centres for carrying out improved weather forecasts. After the expedition, ECCC will use the full suite of observations from AO2018 for model evaluation and development.

WP4 of APPLICATE (Irina Sandu, ECMWF) is coordinating joint experiments (OSEs-FSOIs) with ECCC (Stéphane Laroche) to contribute to YOPP's goal of making recommendations for the optimization of the observing system in polar regions. With growing human activities and

² <https://www.iarpccollaborations.org/news/9953>

the implementation of new METAREAs to provide weather information and forecasts in the Arctic, it is increasingly relevant to examine the value of in situ and satellite observations in high-latitude. The role of the various types of observations in numerical weather prediction at mid-latitude is now well understood. The impact of observations in the Arctic, however, is less clear. This is because terrestrial observations are sparse and satellite observations are affected by ice and snow for which the emissivity properties can be difficult to estimate. Furthermore, there are very few aircraft reports over the polar region, which are now an important source of observations in the northern hemisphere mid-latitude. YOPP provides a good opportunity to examine, among others, the relative importance of satellite and terrestrial observations, the forecast skill in the Arctic with respect to the one in mid-latitude and the impact of observations in high-latitude on the forecast skill at mid-latitude.

Two Special Observing Periods (SOP) were chosen in 2018 to carry out YOPP-related forecasting experiments: the winter period of February to March and the summer period of July to September. During the first SOP, additional radiosondes at 16 operational stations were launched. Radiosondes from non-operational stations and ships as well as buoys from the International Arctic Buoy Programme are planned to be added during the second SOP. The SOPs are long enough to obtain statistically reliable assessment of the impact of the operational and additional observations across a range of different weather types. An international collaboration for conducting observations impact experiments is considered. ECCC plans to assess the impact of observations over the Arctic through Forecast Sensitivity - Observation Impact (FSOI) methods and Observing System Experiments (OSEs). FSOI is a flexible approach to estimate the impact of arbitrary subsets of observations on short-range forecast error. The assessment can be done globally or over a region of interest. No FSOI study has been conducted for the Arctic region yet. The FSOI system developed at ECCC relies on an ensemble of forecasts instead of the adjoint of the forecast model as in several meteorological centres, including ECMWF. The impact of each type of observations over the Arctic will be examined and ranked. Intercomparison of FSOI results between ECCC and ECMWF is envisioned to assess the difference between the two methodologies. It is proposed to run FSOI first on the summer SOP because significant upgrades will be implemented into the ECCC operational data assimilation system in June 2018 and more additional terrestrial observations will be deployed in the Arctic. Moreover, the CAPS model will be coupled with RIOPS. An observing system experiment is a more comprehensive approach to assess the impact of observations by running sets of analyses and forecasts with and without particular subsets of data. The impact at various forecast lead times can be examined whereas the FSOI is restricted to a given short-range lead time (e.g. 24h). However, the OSE approach becomes very expensive if many experiments are carried out to examine the relative importance of several observing networks. In this case, the FSOI is a more effective approach. For a comprehensive review of the relative merits of FSOI and OSE approaches. It is proposed to carry out a few OSEs, which will be coordinated with the other participating meteorological centers in YOPP.

The goal of Work Package 4 in APPLICATE is to provide guidance for a better exploitation of current observing systems in the Arctic and for making recommendation for future optimizations, in order to improve sub-seasonal to interannual Arctic and lower-latitude predictions. Work Package 5 extends the work done in WP4, by quantifying the improved skill provided through APPLICATE, and is expected to provide general guidance for weather and climate predictions in the Arctic and beyond. This will include a systematic

benchmarking of APPLICATE's predictions with respect to existing databases. So far, the following activities have been undertaken with US or Canadian partners in relationship to WP4/WP5 activities:

- A study on methodological aspects of sea-ice data assimilation, involving Prof Cecilia Bitz from the University of Washington, has been published in *Tellus A* (Kimmritz et al., 2018). The study provides recommendation for the design of initialization methods in large-scale climate models. More generally, four institutions (UCL, BSC, NERSC and UW) exchange regularly on topics related to sea-ice data assimilation in order to learn from each other's experience. Another publication is currently under revision (Zhang et al., 2018). In addition, fraternal experiments are planned within the next year, that is, experiments in which data generated by one climate model is assimilated into another.
- Francois Massonnet spent the month of July 2017 in the Department of Atmospheric Sciences at the University of Washington (with Prof. Cecilia Bitz and Dr Edward Blanchard-Wrigglesworth). During his stay, novel process-oriented diagnostics were developed to understand the origin of spread in simulated trend, variability and persistence of sea ice volume. It was found that this spread was caused by the spread in simulated mean sea ice thickness in the central Arctic, thus calling for better observational estimates in that region in order to further constrain model predictions from years to decades. This study is currently under revision (Massonnet et al., 2018).
- Thomas Jung and Francois Massonnet are both involved in the Sea Ice Prediction Network 2 (SIPN2) leadership team. SIPN2 is a US-based initiative to collect and analyse seasonal outlooks of Arctic sea ice from various sources. One of the goals of APPLICATE WP5 is to evaluate the skill of EC-Earth, CNRM, Met Office and ECMWF relative that of the forecasts provided through the SIPN2 database, which includes far more models and various different forecast approaches (e.g. empirical vs dynamical). These SIPN2 data will be used in the skill score Atlas, which is an APPLICATE deliverable due in October 2018 summarising the current status of weather and prediction in the Arctic, and in which the US SIPN2 group collaborates. Furthermore, some APPLICATE partners will contribute to SIPN2 with their own seasonal predictions.

Ed Blockley (MetOffice) visited NCAR for a workshop entitled "Arctic system change" where he talked with the NCAR/CESM group about the heat budget comparisons planned for APPLICATE T1.4. He will also be attending the Polar Prediction Workshop being organised by SIPN2 in May 2018 in Montreal where he will present the work that he's have been doing under WP4 (and have recently submitted to *The Cryosphere*). They will also be submitting an early forecast to SIPN2 as part of the contribution to the workshop. MetOffice provided Arctic sea ice forecasts to SIPN all through last summer as well as providing Antarctic forecasts for the "SIPN South" initiative. In December 2016 Ed Blockley was part of the SIPN post-season action report "action team" that wrote the SIPN 2016 post-season report³ (along with Francois Massonnet, WP4 co-leader). Ed Blockley also attended the SIPN/PPW meeting in Bremerhaven in March 2017, partly organised by SIPN. In January 2018, Ed Blockley was also a panellist at the sea ice prediction stakeholder engagement event co-organised by SIPN (with CliC) at Arctic Frontiers in Tromsø. Finally, it is important to mention that Ed Blockley was also in the USA at the very start of the APPLICATE project as he attended the FAMOS meeting at WHOI at the start of November 2016.

³ <https://www.arcus.org/sipn/sea-ice-outlook/2016/post-season>

There has been very fruitful collaboration between the NorESM-group at MET Norway and the US CESM-program centred around NCAR. The Norwegian Earth System Model (NorESM) is an amended version of the Community Earth System Models (CESMs) developed at a number of universities and science labs in the US. The definition of and production runs with CESM are co-ordinated by the National Center of Atmospheric Research (NCAR) in Boulder, Colorado. The NorESM-group keeps a close contact with NCAR and the CESM-groups, both on a scientific and a technical level. On a quasi-regular basis, the contacts are by e-mail, sometimes by telecons, and by participation in annual working group meetings (AMWG and CCWG in February 2017 and 2018), and in the annual CESM general workshop (June 2017). The main contact points at NCAR are the CESM Chief Scientist (up to Jan 2018: J-F. Lamarque; at present: Gokhan Danabasoglu) and the Working-Group Chairs (in particular AMWG, up to Jan 2018 Rich Neale, at present Julio Bacmeister; and the WAWG, Andrew Gettelman). With respect to polar climate issues, Marika Holland is the main contact point, and there are regular contacts on scientific and technical issues with several, in particular with Cecile Hannay for the development of the CMIP6-version.

Météo France (Rym Msadek) is collaborating with NOAA GFDL in Princeton, USA on sea ice predictability in the Arctic. More specifically they have been working closely with Mitch Bushuk and Michael Winton at GFDL to evaluate the regional skill of Arctic sea ice the GFDL seasonal predictions (see their joint paper in GRL: <https://doi.org/10.1002/2017GL073155>). They also conducted a comprehensive work to compare this regional skill in operational predictions obtained using a perfect model framework, which allows to identify where progress is possible to improve the regional forecasts Arctic with better models and a better initialization. The paper has been revised and is being accepted. This work is not directly funded by APPLICATE but it is relevant to WP5. Mitch Bushuk visited Météo France in Toulouse in March 2017 to discuss possible collaboration to compare the seasonal forecasts of GFDL to those produced by Météo France.

Furthermore, in 2013 Météo France signed a MoU with Environment and Climate Change Canada (ECCC) to develop a cooperation on meteorology, hydrology and oceanography, which is still ongoing. Main points of contact for this effort are Pierre Pellerin (ECCC) and Matthieu Chevallier (MeteoFrance). Under this agreement, there are actual collaborations on ocean-sea ice forecasts (including sea ice modelling and coupling with the atmosphere), snow observations and modelling, and subseasonal to seasonal forecasting (including, but not limited to, projects S2S and FRAMS). These collaborations include sharing of expertise, code, data and also scientific visits. See for example the paper published within the time frame of APPLICATE and which was written as part of this collaboration:

- Chevallier, M., Smith, G., Lemieux, J.-F., Dupont, F., Forget, G., Fujii, Y., Hernandez, F., Msadek, R., Peterson, K.A., Storto, A., Toyoda, T., Valdivieso, M., Vernieres, G., Zuo, H., Balmaseda, M., Chang, Y.-S., Ferry, N., Garric, G., Haines, K., Keeley, S., Kovach, R.M., Kuragano, T., Masina, S., Tang, Y., Tsujino, H., Wang, X, 2017. Intercomparison of the Arctic sea ice cover in global ocean-sea ice reanalyses from the ORA-IP project. *Climate Dynamics*, Special Issue: Ocean Reanalysis, 49(3), 1107-1136, doi:10.1007/s00382-016-2985-y.

Météo France has also shown interest in contributing to the project FRAMS (Forecasting Regional Arctic Sea Ice from a Month to Seasons) coordinated by Bruno Tremblay (McGill University) and Bertrand Denis (ECCC), funded by the MEOPAR Canadian network.

Contribution includes sharing outputs from MF seasonal forecasting system, to serve a proof of concept for the Arctic RCC long range forecasting capabilities.

CNRM has been collaborating with the University of California Irvine (UCI): Julien Cattiaux visited UCI (15/11-20/12/2015) and Yannick Peings visited CNRM (16/08-1/09/2017). The collaboration resulted in several research papers:

- Cattiaux, J., Y. Peings, D. Saint-Martin, N. Trou-Kechout and S.J. Vavrus (2016), Sinuosity of mid-latitude atmospheric flow in a warming world, *Geophysical Research Letters*, 43, 8259–8268. doi:10.1002/2016GL070309
- Douville H., Y. Peings, D. Saint-Martin (2017) Snow-(N)AO relationship revisited over the whole 20th century. *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, 44, 569-577, doi:10.1002/2016GL071584
- Peings Y., H. Douville, J. Colin, D. Saint-Martin, G. Magnusdottir (2017) Snow-(N)AO teleconnection and its modulation by the Quasi-Biennial Oscillation. *J Climate*, 30, 10211-10235, doi:10.1175/JCLI-D-17-0041.1
- Peings, Y., J. Cattiaux, S. Vavrus and G. Magnusdottir (2017), Changes in the mid-latitude atmospheric circulation in the CESM Large Ensemble, *Journal of Climate*, 30, 5943–5960. doi:10.1175/JCLI-D-16-0340.1
- Vavrus, S., F. Wang, J. Martin, J. Francis, Y. Peings and J. Cattiaux (2017), Changes in North American Atmospheric Circulation and Extreme Weather, *Journal of Climate*, 30, 4317–4333. doi:10.1175/JCLI-D-16-0762.1

APPLICATE coordinator Thomas Jung (AWI) and WP3-leader Doug Smith (MetOffice) participated in the US CLIVAR Working Group on Arctic Change and Possible Influence on Mid-Latitude Climate and Weather workshop⁴ at Georgetown University in Washington, DC, on 1-3 February 2017 on behalf of the APPLICATE Consortium to strengthen the link with the working group and to gather recommendations for the WP3 numerical experimentation plan. Recommendations for the modelling community included the creation of a modelling task force to coordinate MIP experiments drawing from the initial planning and discussions of the US CLIVAR Working Group and planned modelling element of the European Horizon 2020 projects (APPLICATE, Blue Action, and PRIMAVERA). A white paper⁵ that has been produced out of the workshop discussions and Working Group activities. In addition to a thorough analysis on the topic, the group provides recommendations based on the workshop findings (see also deliverable D8.5). As the US CLIVAR working group will finish its term in early summer 2018, the APPLICATE team will continue clustering with North American partners in the framework of the PAMIP team, which is co-lead by the APPLICATE-PI Doug Smith.

Doug Smith co-organised the AGCI workshop on the causes and consequences of polar amplification⁶. He also collaborates with US and Canadian scientists in developing PAMIP,

⁴ <https://usclivar.org/meetings/2017-arctic-midlatitude-workshop>

⁵ <https://indd.adobe.com/view/352be82e-9f4b-4637-b45e-9b58665f7a45>

⁶ <https://www.agci.org/event/17s1>

the Polar Amplification Model Intercomparison Project developed by APPLICATE team and endorsed as contribution to CMIP6⁷.

Stockholm University (Gunilla Svensson) has close collaboration with ECCC (Barbara Casati) on model evaluation at supersites. The supersites are using are mainly the IASOA (International Arctic Systems for Observing the Atmosphere) network which is coordinated by Taneil Uttal, NOAA. This work aligns with the goals of APPLICATE to find model biases in processes as well as will possibly lead to identification of cases that can be used within APPLICATE for intercomparison of models on a process level. The inter-comparison includes several of the APPLICATE NWP models (IFS HRES from ECMWF and AROME from Meteo France and MET Norway) in addition to the Canadian ECCC CAPS model set up for YOPP. As part of YOPP a number of operational centres will be performing evaluation of their models at polar super-sites. This involves several APPLICATE partners: ECMWF, Met Norway, University of Stockholm, Meteo France and the Met Office. It will also include collaboration with North American Partners ECCC and NOAA, including members of the IASOA network.

Laurent Terray (CERFACS) was invited to give a lecture in the final CanSISE project workshop last on the 1-3 November 2017 in Victoria, Canada. He is also external collaborator of the CanSISE project, coordinated by Paul Kushner from U. Toronto. The Canadian Sea Ice and Snow Evolution (CanSISE) Network is a 5-year collaborative partnership between researchers from eight Canadian universities (Toronto, York, McGill, Victoria, Guelph, Waterloo, UBC, UNBC) and three partner organizations (the Climate Research Division of Environment Canada, the Canadian Ice Service, and the Pacific Climate Impacts Consortium). The CanSISE Network seeks to advance seasonal to multidecadal prediction of Arctic sea ice and snow in Canada's sub-Arctic, alpine, and seasonally snow covered regions. It will also quantify and exploit, for prediction purposes, the role that Northern Hemisphere snow and sea ice processes play in climate variability and change.

The Polar Prediction School 2018⁸ on weather and climate prediction in the polar regions, organised by APPLICATE WP7 in collaboration with the YOPP, includes several instructors, participants and organisers based in the US (see also deliverable D8.7). Furthermore, it brought together early career scientist from Europe, North America and other countries.

3. FURTHER REPORTS

Monitoring of clustering activities with USA and Canada will be carried out by the WP8 leaders. Two further reports on these activities will be produced in the third and fourth year of the project (i.e., D8.9 due month 36 and D8.10 due month 48).

⁷ <https://applicat.eu/news/104-polar-amplification-model-intercomparison-project-pamip-developed-by-applicate-team-endorsed-as-contribution-to-cmip6>

⁸ <https://www.apecs.is/events/upcoming-event-highlights/polar-prediction-school-2018.html>